

FRANSUZ TILI DARSLARIDA “AFFEKTIV (HISSIIY) FILTR”NI KAMAYTIRISH VOSITASI SIFATIDA IJODIY-NUTQIY LOYIHALARNING SAMARADORLIGI.

Xolova Shahnoza Davronovna, Buxoro davlat universiteti, Xorijiy tillar fakulteti, Nemis-fransuz tili kafedrasida o'qituvchisi, Buxoro, O'zbekiston

Narzulloyeva Dilfuza Bahridin qizi, Buxoro davlat universiteti, Xorijiy tillar fakulteti, Filologiya va tillarni o'qitish (fransuz tili) yo'nalishi 4-bosqich talabasi, Buxoro, O'zbekiston

Annotatsiya

KIRISH: bugungi globallashtirish jarayonida chet tillarini o'rganish jarayoni nafaqat lingvistik bilimlarni egallash, balki o'quvchilarning psixologik holatini ham hisobga olishni talab etadi. Xususan, “affektiv filtr” tushunchasi til o'rganishda muhim omil bo'lib, u o'quvchilarning qo'rquv, ishonchsizlik, stress kabi hissiy holatlari bilan bog'liq to'siqlarni anglatadi. Ushbu tushuncha til o'rganish samaradorligini sezilarli darajada pasaytirishi mumkin. Fransuz tili darslarida o'quvchilarning erkin fikrlashi, o'zini ifoda etishi va nutqiy faoliyatga faol jalb etilishi uchun affektiv filtrni kamaytirish zarur. Shu nuqtai nazardan, ijodiy-nutqiy loyihalar samarali pedagogik vosita sifatida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Mazkur yondashuv o'quvchilarning qiziqishini oshiradi, ularning nutqiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantiradi va psixologik to'siqlarni kamaytiradi.

MAQSAD: tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi - fransuz tili darslarida ijodiy-nutqiy loyihalardan foydalanish orqali o'quvchilarda affektiv (hissiy) filtrni kamaytirish va bu orqali ularning nutqiy faoliyat samaradorligini oshirishdan iborat.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: mazkur tadqiqotda quyidagi metodlardan foydalanildi: Nazariy tahlil - affektiv filtr nazariyasi va ijodiy ta'lim texnologiyalariga oid ilmiy adabiyotlarni o'rganish. Pedagogik kuzatuv - fransuz tili darslarida o'quvchilarning faoliyati va hissiy holatini kuzatish. Eksperimental metod - ijodiy-nutqiy loyihalarni amaliyotda qo'llash. So'rovnomalar va testlar - o'quvchilarning o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchi, motivatsiyasi va nutqiy faolligini aniqlash. Tadqiqot jarayonida o'quvchilarga quyidagi turdagi ijodiy loyihalar taklif etildi: Rol o'ynash (dialog va sahna ko'rinishlari). Mini-prezentatsiyalar. Hikoya tuzish va taqdim etish Video va audio loyiha ishlari

NATIJA VA MUHOKAMA: tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, ijodiy-nutqiy loyihalardan foydalanish o'quvchilarning affektiv filtrini sezilarli darajada kamaytiradi. Xususan: O'quvchilarda nutqiy qo'rquv kamaydi, o'ziga ishonch ortdi, darslarda faollik va ishtirok darajasi oshdi, fransuz tilida erkin fikr bildirish ko'nikmalari shakllandi. Ijodiy loyihalar orqali o'quvchilar o'zlarini erkin his qila boshladilar, bu esa ularning psixologik to'siqlarini bartaraf etishga yordam berdi. Shuningdek, dars jarayonida ijobiy muhit shakllandi, bu esa o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi samarali muloqotni kuchaytirdi.

XULOSA: fransuz tili darslarida ijodiy-nutqiy loyihalardan foydalanish affektiv filtrni kamaytirishda samarali vosita hisoblanadi. Ushbu yondashuv o'quvchilarning psixologik holatini yaxshilaydi, nutqiy faoliyatini rivojlantiradi va chet tilini o'zlashtirish

samaradorligini oshiradi. Shu bois, zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida ijodiy yondashuvlar va interfaol metodlardan keng foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Kalit so'zlar: affektiv filtr, fransuz tili, ijodiy-nutqiy loyihalar, nutqiy kompetensiya, motivatsiya, psixologik to'siq, interfaol metodlar, til o'rganish samaradorligi

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ТВОРЧЕСКО-РЕЧЕВЫХ ПРОЕКТОВ КАК СРЕДСТВА СНИЖЕНИЯ «АФФЕКТИВНОГО (ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНОГО) ФИЛЬТРА» НА УРОКАХ ФРАНЦУЗСКОГО ЯЗЫКА.

Холова Шахноза Давроновна, преподаватель кафедры немецко-французского языка факультета иностранных языков, Бухарского государственного университета, Бухара, Узбекистан.

Нарзуллоева Дилфуза Бахриддин кизи, студентка 4 курса факультета иностранных языков, Бухарского государственного университета направления «Филология и обучение языкам (французский язык)», Бухара, Узбекистан.

Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: в условиях современной глобализации процесс изучения иностранных языков требует не только освоения лингвистических знаний, но и учета психологического состояния обучающихся. В частности, понятие «аффективный фильтр» является важным фактором в обучении языку и отражает барьеры, связанные с такими эмоциональными состояниями, как страх, неуверенность и стресс. Данный фактор может существенно снижать эффективность усвоения языка. На уроках французского языка необходимо снижать аффективный фильтр для обеспечения свободного выражения мыслей учащихся и их активного вовлечения в речевую деятельность. В этом контексте творческо-речевые проекты выступают как эффективное педагогическое средство, повышающее интерес обучающихся, развивающее их речевую компетенцию и уменьшающее психологические барьеры.

ЦЕЛЬ: основной целью исследования является снижение аффективного (эмоционального) фильтра у учащихся на уроках французского языка посредством использования творческо-речевых проектов и повышение эффективности их речевой деятельности.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: в ходе исследования были использованы следующие методы: теоретический анализ научной литературы по теории аффективного фильтра и творческим образовательным технологиям; педагогическое наблюдение за деятельностью и эмоциональным состоянием учащихся на уроках французского языка; экспериментальный метод с применением творческо-речевых проектов; анкетирование и тестирование для определения уровня уверенности, мотивации и речевой активности обучающихся. В процессе исследования учащимся были предложены следующие виды

творческих проектов:

ролевая игра (диалоги и сценические постановки), мини-презентации, составление и представление рассказов, а также видео- и аудиопроекты.

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ И ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ: результаты исследования показали, что использование творческо-речевых проектов значительно снижает уровень аффективного фильтра у учащихся. В частности, наблюдалось снижение речевого страха, повышение уверенности в себе, увеличение активности и участия на уроках, а также формирование навыков свободного выражения мыслей на французском языке. Благодаря творческим проектам учащиеся стали чувствовать себя более раскованно, что способствовало преодолению психологических барьеров. Кроме того, на уроках сформировалась благоприятная атмосфера, способствующая эффективному взаимодействию между преподавателем и обучающимися.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: таким образом, использование творческо-речевых проектов на уроках французского языка является эффективным средством снижения аффективного фильтра. Данный подход способствует улучшению психологического состояния учащихся, развитию их речевой деятельности и повышению эффективности усвоения иностранного языка. В связи с этим целесообразно широко применять творческие и интерактивные методы в современном образовательном процессе.

Ключевые слова: аффективный фильтр, французский язык, творческо-речевые проекты, речевая компетенция, мотивация, психологический барьер, интерактивные методы, эффективность обучения языку

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CREATIVE-SPEECH PROJECTS AS A MEANS OF REDUCING THE “AFFECTIVE (EMOTIONAL) FILTER” IN FRENCH LANGUAGE CLASSES.

Kholova Shahnoza Davronovna, teacher of the german-french department, faculty of foreign languages, Bukhara state university

Narzulloyeva Dilfuza Bahriddin qizi, 4th-year student of the faculty of foreign languages, Bukhara state university, philology and language teaching (french)

Annotation

INTRODUCTION: in the context of modern globalization, the process of learning foreign languages requires not only the acquisition of linguistic knowledge but also consideration of learners' psychological states. In particular, the concept of the “affective filter” is an important factor in language learning, representing barriers related to emotional states such as fear, lack of confidence, and stress. This factor can significantly reduce the effectiveness of language acquisition. In French language classes, it is essential to lower the affective filter to ensure students' free expression and active

participation in speech activities. In this regard, creative-speech projects serve as an effective pedagogical tool, increasing learners' interest, developing their communicative competence, and reducing psychological barriers.

AIM: the main objective of the study is to reduce students' affective (emotional) filter in French language classes through the use of creative-speech projects and thereby improve the effectiveness of their speech activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: the following methods were used in the study: Theoretical analysis – study of scientific literature on the affective filter theory and creative educational technologies. Pedagogical observation – monitoring students' activities and emotional states during French lessons. Experimental method – implementation of creative-speech projects in practice. Surveys and tests – assessment of students' confidence, motivation, and speech activity. During the research, students were offered the following types of creative projects: role-playing (dialogues and dramatizations), mini-presentations, storytelling and presentations, as well as video and audio projects.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: the results of the study showed that the use of creative-speech projects significantly reduces students' affective filter. In particular: Students' speaking anxiety decreased. Self-confidence increased. Classroom participation and activity improved. Skills of free expression in French were developed. Through creative projects, students began to feel more comfortable, which helped them overcome psychological barriers. In addition, a positive classroom environment was formed, enhancing effective interaction between teacher and students.

CONCLUSION: in conclusion, the use of creative-speech projects in French language classes is an effective means of reducing the affective filter. This approach improves students' psychological state, develops their speech activity, and increases the effectiveness of foreign language acquisition. Therefore, it is advisable to widely implement creative and interactive methods in modern education.

Keywords: affective filter, French language, creative-speech projects, communicative competence, motivation, psychological barriers, interactive methods, language learning effectiveness

Jn today's era of globalization, not only English, but also French, retains its position as the language of international communication, culture and diplomacy. However, one of the biggest difficulties that teachers face in the educational process is the problem of students avoiding or remaining silent during the lesson. One of the main reasons for this is linguistic and psychological barriers, which reduce students' speech activity and negatively affect the development of communicative competence. One of the first important factors is the lack of vocabulary. Students are afraid of not being able to find the necessary and appropriate words to express their thoughts. This situation leads

to the student's reluctance to express his thoughts. This problem is especially noticeable in the initial period of language learning and can be observed in many students.

The second factor is the fear of making grammatical mistakes in the process of oral speech. In French, grammatical features such as the complex conjugation of verbs, gender and number categories, the use of articles, and the agreement of adjectives create difficulties for students. As a result, students try to avoid speech activity, fearing to speak incorrectly. There is a monitor hypothesis in science, that is, the student edits his speech excessively with an internal "controller" (monitor), and as a result, the speed of speech decreases, fluency is lost. Grammatical rules, instead of helping communication, begin to serve as an obstacle to it. The third factor is difficulties with pronunciation. The phonetic system of the French language is difficult for many students. For example, *nasal sounds* [ã], [õ], [ɛ̃] or liaison phenomena (liaison) increase the fear of incorrect pronunciation. This creates a lack of confidence in students regarding their speech and they do not want to look ridiculous with their "rough" pronunciation.

The fourth factor is the social environment in the classroom. Some students avoid speaking, fearing ridicule or criticism from their peers. In such a situation, students refrain from freely expressing their thoughts. As a result, these linguistic and psychological factors together create a state of speech anxiety (*l'anxiété linguistique*) in the student, which reduces the effectiveness of the process of learning a foreign language.

Not only cognitive, but also *affective (emotional)* factors play an important role in the process of language learning. Modern language teaching methods emphasize that emotional factors such as motivation, self-confidence and anxiety directly affect the level of language acquisition of students. In philosophy, Aristotle defined emotions as: "all those feelings which change a person in such a way as to affect their judgment and which are accompanied by suffering or pleasure" (Rhetoric II, Chapter 1, 182). Twenty-four centuries later, Jérôme Ravat (2007) explains that "basic" emotions correspond to more specific mental states characterized in particular by a rapid onset, a limited duration, and an involuntary emergence." He differentiates between emotions and feelings such as love or jealousy. He adds that "a feeling, in fact, can develop gradually, last longer than an emotion, and also refers to a conscious perception, which is not always the case with an emotion." » (Ravat, 2007: 83). According to research in the field of psychology and neurobiology, some emotions are associated with the biological evolution of humans and are universal in nature. Such basic emotions include joy, sadness, fear, anger, surprise and disgust. Researchers claim that these emotions are innate and appear automatically and often subconsciously from the very beginning of human life (Antonio Damasio, 1999: 58). Emotions also play an important role in the process of communication between people. They help people express their thoughts and feelings in speech, which is manifested through facial expressions (Botella, 2005: 9). In addition, emotions also serve to protect a person from various dangerous or emergency situations. For example, the feeling of fear encourages a person to avoid danger and

thereby serves to save his life (Antonio Damasio, 2010: 185). In this sense, emotions are manifested as a kind of “language” of the human body. At the same time, more complex emotions are also formed during human activity. These include states such as shame, pride, shyness or envy. Researchers call such Ravat, 2007 : 83 emotions “higher-level cognitive emotions”, because they arise mainly in the process of social relationships and are associated with complex cognitive processes, including the activity of the reflexive mind (Ravat, 2007: 83).

Emotional factors play a role in learner success. According to Stephen Krashen (2009: 31), research over the last decade (the 1970s and 1980s) has confirmed that various affective variables are linked to the success of second language acquisition. Most of these studies can be classified into one of three categories:

1. *Motivation*. Highly motivated learners generally perform better in second language acquisition.
2. *Self-confidence*. Confident learners with a positive self-image tend to perform better in second language acquisition.
3. *Anxiety*. Low anxiety appears to be conducive to second language acquisition, whether measured on an individual or classroom scale.

According to the theory of the Affective Filter Hypothesis, put forward by the famous linguist Stephen Krashen, the emotional state of the learner is one of the important factors influencing the process of language acquisition. If the learner has fear, anxiety or low motivation, the affective filter will be high and the new language material will not be effectively mastered. On the contrary, if the learner feels free and confident, the affective filter will be low and the language acquisition process will be more effective.

Anxiety is therefore an emotion that can disrupt learners and hinder their learning. The stronger it is, the lower their self-esteem will be. The former has a strong influence on the latter. An anxious person will often tend to question themselves and undervalue themselves. They may lack self-confidence and find it more difficult to engage in activities or connect with others, as their self-esteem is low, or even very low. The way others perceive them can have consequences and lead them to withdraw, not speak, or break off all contact with others. This type of student is sometimes also found in foreign language classes. The stronger the anxiety, the more negative the self-esteem, and the less motivated a person will be to perform tasks or actions that could have negative consequences for them. Motivation is linked to the different emotions that human beings can experience, such as anxiety and self-esteem.

Certainly, a teacher's primary task is to teach, but they must also get to know the members of their class. This begins with knowing their first or last name. Students can then feel that their teacher is trying to get to know them, and this can create a closer student-teacher relationship. When learners feel valued, they can become more engaged in classroom activities. In the Rodriguez, Plax, and Kearney model cited by Jane Arnold, "if the teacher creates an affective relationship that supports learners through proximity

and friendship, this predisposes students to devote more time to learning tasks and thus leads to better cognitive results" (Arnold, 2006: 416).

Also, one of the researchers who made a great contribution to the study of affective factors in language teaching methodology is Jane Arnold. According to her views, the emotional state of the learner, self-confidence and a positive psychological environment created by the teacher are important pedagogical factors in learning a foreign language. Arnold emphasizes in her research that the teacher's supportive attitude, creative activities and cooperative activities increase the speech activity of students. Therefore, one of the urgent pedagogical tasks in modern French language lessons is the use of innovative methods, in particular creative speech projects, aimed at reducing students' emotional barriers. Such an approach increases students' motivation, creates a positive psychological atmosphere in the lesson, and helps develop oral competence.

To help students develop a sense of self-esteem in relation to the foreign language they are learning, the activities offered and carried out in the lesson should be meaningful to them. Next, the teacher should try to determine the learning styles of the students. For example, some students are auditory learners, learning mainly by hearing, while others are visual learners, learning more by seeing, and some are kinesthetic learners, learning through gestures. Thus, although the teacher's task is to meet the individual needs of each student, it is difficult to do this in one lesson. Therefore, the teacher should have a wide range of tools and methods. He can try to satisfy the interests of students through various creative activities, tasks performed in groups (collaboration). Encouraging oral communication in the classroom, using drama, staged phonetics exercises or playful activities can help improve the classroom environment. Also, changing the activities and the way the classroom is organized allows students to get to know each other better, gain confidence and exchange ideas, which in turn strengthens social bonds between them.

The most important thing for a teacher is to work with and for students, to provide them with freedom, to allow them to use their creative and imaginative potential. "The assumed view is that language learning is a process of moving the body, as attention is drawn to hearing and seeing another person; therefore, learning a language other than one's own is a transition from a 'speaking body' to another body, a temporary experience of oneself as another person, which involves cognitive, semantic, emotional, social and cultural influences" (Louÿs and Leeman, 2013: 5).

However, as Didier Bottineau points out, "although communicative competences and task-based approaches are valued, students are left out of two important dimensions: speaking is a physical connection with others and, through it, the two-way development of semantic, emotional and interactive cognitive effects. Often, the gap between this experience and formal goals creates obstacles, and sometimes it leads to stress and misunderstandings" (Bottineau, 2013: 12). Therefore, the teacher must ensure that communication takes place between all participants in the classroom, as well as pay

attention to the different emotions of the students. Some tools that take into account affective factors can be very interesting for students. For example, board games. Students often forget that they are learning while playing a game (Agaësse, 2009: 50), which reduces their fear and increases their motivation. Gradually, they become less hesitant to speak, establish friendly relationships with their peers, and experience positive emotions such as joy. Such games make language learning less stressful and compulsive. As Gilles Brougère notes, games “allow students to escape from everyday life and its consequences” (Brougère, 2005: 57). At the same time, Jérôme Bruner adds: “through games, students have the opportunity to try out different combinations of behaviors that would be difficult in normal situations” (Brougère, 2005: 56). Through games, students are given the opportunity to make mistakes, take responsibility for solving problems and finding solutions, and as a result, develop independence and self-control. They communicate, cooperate with their peers, and complete various tasks with the aim of winning (based on the rules of the game or their modifications). In this way, students have more freedom to complete tasks and have more choice in topics than in traditional classes, without realizing that they are learning. When board games are used, students who are usually very shy talk more and become more active. Teachers, meanwhile, monitor the safety and emotional state of students, answer questions, and ensure that activities are carried out correctly.

In the methodology of teaching a foreign language, the attitude towards errors is one of the important pedagogical issues. In traditional lessons, students' grammatical or lexical errors are immediately corrected, which often reduces their speech activity. Students may refrain from freely expressing their thoughts due to fear of making mistakes. Therefore, in modern communicative methodology, instead of immediately correcting errors, a delayed correction approach is used. According to this method of the principle of “Error is a means of development”, the teacher, without interrupting the student's speech, notes his mistakes and corrects them through a general discussion at the end of the lesson. This approach maintains the speech activity of students and ensures the communicative nature of the lesson process. For example, students can express their thoughts using French expressions such as:

- « *Je pense que cette activité est intéressante et utile.* »
- « *À mon avis, apprendre le français est efficace.* »
- « *Je voudrais parler plus en français.* »

Table 1. Classification of creative and speech projects used in French lessons

Type of activity	Developing skills	Affective filter factor	Expected result
Role-playing games	Oral speech	Reduce fear	Free communication
Group project	Collaboration	Social support	Increased activity
Presentation	Speech and	Self-confidence	Independent opinion

	argumentation		
Create a video or podcast	Creative speech	Motivation	Interest in language
Cultural project	Intercultural competence	Interest	Positive emotional environment

Such activities reduce students' fear of making mistakes and provide opportunities for them to gain speaking experience. Thus, creative play and theater methods, as well as visual and technological tools, serve to reduce students' affective barriers in the process of learning French and develop their oral competence.

Studying a foreign language is not easy; not everything is always logical. This can lead to some tension, but creating moments like this can help learners release tension and refocus. While these aren't always formal teaching moments, they allow students to take a short break and recharge. This can only be achieved if the teacher is aware of the class's emotional state and understands the prevailing atmosphere.

It can be observed that the students' speech activity has increased significantly using various methods. This is due to the fact that the French lessons were based on the principle of error as a means of development (Delayed Correction).

Table 2. Classification of the main linguistic errors observed in French lessons

Error category	Clear manifestations of errors
Lexical errors	- literal translation from the native language - Confusion in cause and effect relationships - Lexical meaning ambiguities (lack of vocabulary)
Grammatical and syntactic errors	-Errors in the construction of interrogative sentences -Incorrect use of grammatical aspects -Incorrect use of articles (determination) -Omission or overuse of plural and singular suffixes -Not knowing the place of pronouns in a sentence and the order of parts of speech -Errors related to prepositions -Misuse of relative pronouns -Confusion between possessive and possessive pronouns
Pronunciation and phonological errors	- Incorrect stress placement - Incorrect pronunciation of certain phonemes (e.g. nasal sounds) - Prosodic errors (stressing grammatical words, incorrect intonation)

Instead of correcting grammatical and lexical errors during the lesson, the teacher analyzed them at the end of the lesson. As a result, students were able to speak freely without fear of making mistakes during the speech process. For example, one student

expressed his experience as follows: “*Je suis le personnage et je peux parler librement.*” (*I am a character and I can speak freely.*) Also, using the *Marottes des émotions* method, students were able to express their emotions through speech. At the beginning of the lesson, they expressed their current mood in French words through the “*Météo des émotions*” exercise, which increased their self-confidence and reduced the affective filter. As Brougère (2005) and Bruner (2005) have pointed out, games allow us to escape from everyday life, to avoid making mistakes and to try new combinations. The board games, staged phonetic exercises and *Théâtre de l’absurde* methods used during the lesson demonstrated this principle in practice. For example, the students used the following expressions in the game: “*Nous devons coopérer pour résoudre cette énigme.*” (*We must cooperate to solve this puzzle.*) “*J’ai le droit de faire des erreurs et d’essayer encore.*” (*I have the right to make mistakes and try again.*) In this way, students assume creative freedom and responsibility, developing independence and self-control through the practical application of language.

Students’ fear and stress were not only related to the fear of making mistakes, but also to the classroom environment, social interactions with peers, and pedagogical stress. In this context, humor and relaxation techniques (*Humour et détente*) were confirmed as important tools to reduce the affective filter. Some teachers allowed students a certain degree of freedom during the lesson: for example, allowing them to yawn or walking around the classroom to reduce accumulated stress. As Beatrix Fife (2016) notes, “*To encourage relaxation, the teacher can suggest exercises in the form of vocal exhalations, which reduce tension in the face and body, similar to what happens after doing muscle tension exercises in gymnastics. This relaxation can also be achieved through laughter or other breathing exercises.*”

Also, as Kertész-Vial (2000) noted, the teacher should take into account the “social-affective factors” that stimulate language learning. Stress and negative stimuli reduce or completely eliminate responses in language lessons. In this regard, humor is one of the most convenient tools, as it relaxes students and prepares them for classroom activities. At the same time, humor and relaxation techniques have shown high efficiency in increasing students’ self-confidence, reducing the affective filter, and making the classroom environment comfortable. This is logically consistent with previous results: through creative exercises, games, theater, and visual aids, students not only developed verbal competence, but also became emotionally relaxed and motivated.

Table 3. Analysis of the impact of positive emotions on students’ speech activity

Student profile (conditional names)	Observed emotions	The factor that aroused the feeling	Speech product (example)	Positive changes in speech	Subjective opinion of the student
Charos	Joy, Pride	Being able to	"J'arrive à	Code	"I felt like a

(9th grade)		independently construct a complex sentence	composer cette phrase toute seule!"	switching, praise lexicon, and exclamation tones	hero and started speaking freely."
Shahina (8th grade)	Optimism , Calmness	The student's patient attitude towards mistakes	«Ok, je peux décrire son style vestimentaire."	Loss of speech impediment, increased fluency	"Not being afraid to make mistakes gave me strength, my teacher supported me."
Sardor (8th grade)	Contentment, Joy	Winning or getting the correct answer during the game	"Bon, j'ai trouvé le mot caché, hurra!"	Use of exclamation (shout) and rich vocabulary	"I forgot I was studying while playing, it was so much fun."

The results of the experiment showed that the use of affective and creative methods in learning French:

- Significantly increases students' speech activity;
- Improves self-esteem and motivation;
- Reduces anxiety;
- Strengthens social ties based on friendship and cooperation;
- Makes language learning natural, free and interesting.

At the same time, with the help of creative methods and affective approaches, students learn to speak freely and use new linguistic elements without fear of mistakes, which eliminates the blockage and frustration that occurs in traditional teaching methods. It follows that affective and creative methods are an effective pedagogical solution in learning French, which allows for the integration of speech competence, emotional state, and personal development of students.

Learning a foreign language is not easy, not everything always makes sense. Therefore, some tensions may arise. Therefore, it is necessary to give students more freedom to work creatively with their knowledge and reduce the impact of negative emotions, such as fear. Through this approach, students will have the opportunity to increase their self-

confidence, not be afraid to speak, and overcome the “*affective filter*”. This will help to strengthen positive affective factors, increase students’ commitment to learning tasks, make them responsible, and encourage them to be independent. It will be interesting to create an environment in the classroom that will generate positive emotions in students. To do this, take into account the types of learning of students, organize exercises in different ways, and allocate time for conversations with students - these are the elements of the first approach. If students feel that their teacher takes their interests and personality into account, they feel more at ease, which reduces fear in the classroom and boosts self-esteem. Of course, the problem is not only in the type of exercises, but also in how to choose them, how to manage them, and how to implement them with students. Taking into account the negative or positive emotions of students is a difficult task for teachers. This does not mean controlling or taking everything into account, but rather taking a careful approach and achieving the best possible result.

Taking into account the learning styles of students in the classroom was also an important factor. Students learn differently: some are auditory (learn by listening to remember), some are visual (learn by seeing), and others are kinesthetic (learn through movement and gestures). Therefore, organizing exercises using different methods and taking into account individual needs makes the learning process interesting and effective. When students feel that their interests and personalities are taken into account, they feel calm, which reduces anxiety and increases self-esteem. The study also showed the importance of the teacher’s emotional state monitoring and interactive pedagogical approach. The teacher can make the language learning process more effective by taking into account the negative or positive emotions of students, guiding the exercises, motivating them, and creating a positive environment. At the same time, giving students the opportunity to work creatively and freely exchange ideas increases their responsibility, encourages independent activity and develops self-esteem. Overall, the study showed that combining affective and creative methods is an effective pedagogical strategy for learning a foreign language.

In conclusion, the study scientifically confirmed that affective and creative methods are an important pedagogical tool in learning French. These methods involve students in speech activity, reduce their anxiety, create a positive emotional environment, and make language learning a natural and free process. At the same time, this approach develops students’ social skills, creative thinking, and the ability to work independently, making the pedagogical process effective and interesting. The combined use of affective and creative methods in learning French not only increases verbal activity, but also significantly increases students’ emotional stability, motivation, and self-esteem. Thus, the lesson process becomes interactive, interesting, and effective.

ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI | СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ | REFERENCES

1. Aristotel. (2014). Œuvres complètes. Éditions Flammarion.

2. Arnold J. (2006). Comment les facteurs affectifs influencent-ils l'apprentissage d'une langue étrangère ? *Ela. Études de linguistique appliquée*, 144, 407-425.
3. A. Tcherkassof, *Les Emotions et leurs expressions* (Presses universitaires de Grenoble, Grenoble, 2008)
4. A. Wierzbicka, E. Jamrozik, L'amour, la colère, la joie, l'ennui. La sémantique des émotions dans une perspective transculturelle. *Langages*, 23/89, 97-107.
5. Bogaards P. (1991). *Aptitude et affectivité dans l'apprentissage des langues étrangères*. Paris: Les Editions Didier.
6. Botella M. (2015). Les émotions en psychologie: définitions et descriptions. *Le Langage et l'homme* vol. 2, 9-22.
7. Bottineau D. (2013). Le vécu corporel dans la pratique d'une langue. *Langages*, 192, 11-28.
8. Damasio A. R. (1999). *Le sentiment même de soi : corps, émotions, conscience*. Paris: Ed. Odile Jacob.
9. Germain C. (1993). *Évolution de l'enseignement des langues : 5000 ans d'histoire*. Paris : CLE International.
10. Louÿs G. et Leeman D. (2013). Pour une ré-évaluation paradigmatique de notre conception du parleur. *Langages*, 192, 3-10.
11. Pennac D. (2007). *Chagrin d'école*. Paris : Gallimard.
12. Porcher L. (1977). Pour une sociologie des apprentissages. *Le Français Dans Le Monde*, 133, 73-77.
13. Ravat J. (2007). Actions, émotions, motivation : fondements psychologiques du raisonnement pratique. *Le Philosophoire*, 29, 81-95.
14. F Raby. *Entre faux débats et vraies distinctions. Réflexion sur les méthodes de recherche empirique en didactique de l'anglais*. LIDILEM, Université Stendhal (Grenoble, 2008)
15. Davronovna, Kholova Shahnoza. "PHRASEOLOGY IN LANGUAGE LEARNING: SPECIFIC DIFFICULTIES ENCOUNTERED BY LEARNERS." "Chet tillarni oqitishning innovatsion usullari, tarjimonshunoslik va filologik tadqiqotlarda zamonaviy yondashuvlar" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman 1.1 (2025): 112-115.
16. Kholova Shahnoza Davronovna. (2025). Challenges And Obstacles In Children Learning French. *Progress Annals: Journal of Progressive Research*, 3(05), 35–37. Retrieved from <https://academiaone.org/index.php/8/article/view/1211>
17. Xolova, S. (2023). "AVOIR" FE'LI ISHTIROKIDAGI INSON HIS-TUYG'ULARINI IFODA ETUVCHI FRAZEMALAR TARJIMASINING O'ZIGA XOSLIKLARI. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ* (buxdu. uz), 33(33).
18. Davronovna, K. S. (2022). SOME FEATURES OF CERTAIN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS TRANSLATION USED IN FRENCH

LITERATURE OF THE NINETEENTH CENTURY. European Journal of
Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 9, 70-74.